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Abstract Book

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SDGs in healthcare organisations – for better environment and better health

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Context

The global challenges of today are numerous, big and extremely complicated. Mass non-communicable diseases are a constantly growing problem with an emphasis on malignant diseases, cardiovascular diseases and other chronic diseases. At the same time, it does not eliminate the threat represented by infectious diseases. Health systems are constantly facing challenges. They are entrapped between humanity and empathy and caught by economic constraints while aiming to provide quality services. Growing poverty, disrupted environment, conflicts and migration, have a direct impact on the work process and pose new demands to health organisations, primarily to hospitals that require quality and sophisticated infrastructure. How SDGs can be a useful guide to better hospitals?

Methods

17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) represent a universal call to contribute comprehensively to solving global challenges, in order to eradicate poverty, ensure peace and prosperity for all, protect environment and also exercise the right to health and health protection.

In this paper, an analytical approach was used in identifying the connection between certain goals of sustainable development and health organisations in order to improve the quality of service, as well as the sustainability of the organisation itself (and its infrastructure).

Results

The paper points to a solid connection not only to SDG 3 (Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages), but also to other goals, which in different environments and conditions can be of various intensity. Nevertheless connections are strong with other goals as well: 1 (End poverty in all its forms everywhere), 2 (End hunger, food security, improved nutrition), 4 (Inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning), 6 (Sustainable management of water and sanitation), 7 (Access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy), 8 (economic growth, full and productive employment), 9 (Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster innovation), 10 (Reduce inequality within and among countries), 11 (Make cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable), 13 (Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts), 16 (Peaceful, inclusive societies, access to justice build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions), 17 (The global partnership for sustainable development).

Discussion and conclusion

The mutual interconnection of causally related links of particular SDGs can be used to achieve improvement in health organisations. SDGs as a tool can also be applied in circumstances where a large range of indicators is present in relation to the specific criteria being observed. This also depends on the level of development (country, region, local self-government) and other conditions, such as migration, climate change, energy capacity, water supply, food quality and nutrition. With all human resources, these external factors affect the hospital primary task - quality of health services and satisfaction of patients and employees. Today's hospitals are exposed to the limitation of financial and resources that can affect the quality of work and the treatment of patients. Analytical approach to SDGs can identify the challenges that the hospital is exposed to and, through careful planning, transformation, investment in certain components, it will contribute to sustainability and more successful outcomes in providing health services in the short and long term. The use of SDGs in hospitals can also be considered as one strategic approach to achieve better results with long-term care of resources and infrastructure.